

IoT-ID: Deterministic Device Identity from Hybrid Network Fingerprinting

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Abstract. *This paper presents IoT-ID, a deterministic fingerprinting system for IoT device identification based on network traffic analysis. By combining passive and active measurements into a canonical multi-layer representation and applying cryptographic hashing, IoT-ID derives stable and reproducible device identities without relying on training data. The integration of application-layer metadata with transport-layer signatures resolves collisions between devices with indistinguishable network stacks, enabling consistent identification across heterogeneous environments. Results confirm the feasibility and effectiveness of deterministic fingerprinting, while highlighting limitations in non-IoT systems due to privacy mechanisms and software homogeneity.*

1. Introduction

The rapid proliferation of IoT devices in operational networks has increased the complexity of device identification and asset management. Traditional identifiers such as IP and MAC addresses are unreliable because they can be dynamically reassigned, spoofed, or obfuscated by privacy mechanisms, hindering the construction of consistent and auditable inventories. In this context, device fingerprinting has emerged as a non-intrusive alternative based on observable network characteristics or intrinsic device properties.

Despite significant advances, existing fingerprinting approaches still present fundamental limitations. Many rely on machine learning models to classify devices from traffic patterns or behavioral features [Safi et al. 2022, Sánchez et al. 2021]. Although effective for coarse-grained classification, these methods are probabilistic, depend on representative datasets and retraining, and often struggle to distinguish devices at fine granularity, such as specific models or instances [Wan et al. 2023]. In parallel, hardware- and network-based features are often unstable, being affected by environmental conditions, firmware updates, workload dynamics, and runtime variability [Kumar and Paul 2023, Zhang et al. 2025, Safi et al. 2022]. In addition, there is still no clear consensus on which attributes remain consistently discriminative across heterogeneous settings [Sheng et al. 2025].

Current approaches also fail to guarantee uniqueness and determinism. Devices sharing similar communication stacks may produce indistinguishable fingerprints when only transport-layer or statistical features are considered, leading to collisions and ambiguity [Wan et al. 2023]. Even hybrid methods remain dependent on probabilistic inference and do not ensure consistent identities across repeated observations. The absence of canonical representations further limits reproducibility and comparability across experiments and deployments [Safi et al. 2022].

To address these limitations, this work presents IoT-ID¹ as an initial step toward deterministic and reproducible device identification in IoT environments. The proposed approach systematically combines discriminative fields extracted from active scanning tools (e.g., *nmap*) and passive fingerprinting tools (e.g., *p0f*) to construct canonical representations that generate unique fingerprints in conventional WiFi IoT networks. Unlike prior approaches, IoT-ID does not rely on training data, emphasizing interpretability, reproducibility, and consistency across executions.

IoT-ID also adopts a temporal perspective: fingerprints are considered valid at a given time instant t and may evolve due to firmware, software, or environmental changes. As part of the broader IoTedu² architecture, the tool maintains a historical record of device signatures, allowing changes to be interpreted as meaningful events rather than noise. This perspective enables IoT-ID to support not only device identification but also continuous monitoring and security analysis in IoT WiFi networks.

2. Related Work

IoT device identification through fingerprinting has been widely explored using network traffic characteristics, behavioral patterns, and intrinsic device properties. Traffic-based approaches typically rely on features such as packet sizes, inter-arrival times, and protocol signatures to construct behavioral profiles [Wan et al. 2023, Aksoy and Gunes 2019]. Passive techniques enable non-intrusive identification, while more recent methods incorporate machine learning to capture complex communication patterns [Aksoy and Gunes 2019]. Despite their effectiveness in controlled settings, these approaches present key limitations, including strong dependence on representative datasets, the need for continuous retraining, limited interpretability, and sensitivity to traffic variability. Moreover, methods based solely on network-level attributes often fail to distinguish devices with similar communication stacks, resulting in low granularity and frequent fingerprint collisions.

More advanced solutions attempt to mitigate these issues by combining active and passive data collection or incorporating hardware-level features to improve discriminative power [Wan et al. 2023, Kohli et al. 2024]. However, they introduce additional complexity, may require direct device access, and remain sensitive to environmental variations. Overall, existing approaches predominantly focus on classification or probabilistic inference rather than on the construction of stable, reproducible device identities [Chowdhury and Abas 2022, Sánchez et al. 2021]. The lack of formal mechanisms for feature canonicalization and deterministic identifier generation further limits reproducibility and comparability across experiments. As summarized in Table 1, no current solution consistently provides unique, stable, and deterministic fingerprints.

3. IoT-ID: Architecture

In contrast to prior fingerprinting approaches based on probabilistic inference, training data, or single-layer observations, IoT-ID is designed to construct **deterministic, reproducible, and multi-layer device identities**. The architecture addresses key limitations

¹https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc26_fingerprint

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Table 1. Comparison of fingerprinting approaches

Work	Type of Collection	ML	Attribute Source	Deterministic
[Gao et al. 2010]	Passive	✗	RF / Temporal	✗
[Aksoy and Gunes 2019]	Passive	✓	Network Traffic	✗
[Wan et al. 2023]	Hybrid	✓	Network Traffic	✗
[Kohli et al. 2024]	Active	✓	Hardware (SRAM)	✗
IoT-ID - this work	Hybrid	✗	Network Traffic	✓

identified in the literature: (i) lack of uniqueness in devices with indistinguishable network stacks, (ii) instability of behavioral features, and (iii) absence of canonical representations for reproducible fingerprint generation. To this end, IoT-ID integrates active and passive measurements and applies a canonicalization process that converts volatile observations into stable and comparable identifiers.

Figure 1. Overview of the fingerprinting tool architecture

As shown in Figure 1, the IoT-ID pipeline is organized into four phases. In **active probing and device discovery**, IoT-ID combines declarative and behavioral sources. Metadata is collected via UPnP (*Universal Plug and Play*), capturing application-layer attributes such as `manufacturer` and `model_name`. In parallel, `nping` triggers TCP SYN responses from the target device, enabling feature extraction even in lowtraffic or idle scenarios.

In **traffic capture and observation**, network traffic is collected with `dumpcap` over a configurable time window. Rather than relying on aggregate behavioral statistics, IoT-ID extracts protocol-level and negotiation-specific attributes, reducing sensitivity to workload variability and improving stability across repeated executions. Next, in **feature extraction (multi-layer representation)**, the captured PCAP is processed with `p0f` and `tshark` to obtain transport-layer signatures and packet-level attributes. This phase produces a multi-layer representation that combines application-layer metadata (L7), such as `manufacturer`, `model`, and `service` descriptors, with transport-layer signatures (L3/L4), including `MSS`, `TTL`, `window size`, `TCP options`, and `SYN/SYN-ACK` signatures. This hybrid view allows IoT-ID to distinguish devices that would remain ambiguous if only one layer were considered.

Finally, in **canonicalization and deterministic hashing**, the extracted attributes are normalized to remove temporal noise and non-deterministic variations, then transformed into a canonical representation in a consistent and ordered form. The fingerprint at time t is defined as $FP_t = \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}_t))$, where \mathcal{A}_t is the set of observed attributes, $\mathcal{C}(\cdot)$ is a deterministic canonicalization function, and $\mathcal{H}(\cdot)$ is a cryptographic hash function (e.g., SHA-256). Guided by the attribute taxonomy in Table 2, the canonicalization distinguishes stable from dynamic features, enabling reproducible fingerprints under equivalent conditions while preserving sensitivity to meaningful device changes over time.

Table 2. Attribute Taxonomy for Canonical IoT Fingerprinting

Layer	Source	Attribute	Can change?	Justification / Description
L7	nmap	manufacturer	No	The manufacturer is a static hardware property.
L7	nmap	model_name	No	The physical model remains unchanged after updates.
L7	nmap	server	Yes	Firmware updates often modify the UPnP server or SDK version.
L7	nmap	name	Yes	Typically a user-defined or application-defined string.
L4	p0f	server_synack_raw_sig_set	Yes	Kernel changes (e.g., Linux 4.x to 5.x) alter TCP signatures.
L4	p0f	client_syn_raw_sig_set	Yes	Follows the same kernel-dependent behavior.
L3/L4	pcap_syn	mss	No	Typically fixed by hardware and network interface MTU.
L3/L4	pcap_syn	window_size	Yes	Firmware updates may modify TCP buffer configurations.
L3/L4	pcap_syn	ttl	No	The base value (e.g., 64) is consistent across most Linux/Android systems.
L3/L4	pcap_syn	ws	Yes	The <i>Window Scale</i> factor may be enabled or adjusted in newer versions.
L4	pcap_syn	sack_perm	Yes	SACK support may be introduced through performance improvements.
L4	pcap_syn	ts_present	Yes	<i>Timestamp</i> support depends on kernel configuration.

Attribute Taxonomy, Temporal Stability, and Security Semantics

To address instability issues observed in prior work, IoT-ID distinguishes between **static** and **dynamic** attributes, as summarized in Table 2. Static attributes, such as manufacturer, model name, MSS, and baseline TTL, form the identity core of the Canon String and ensure long-term consistency. Dynamic attributes, including TCP window size, kernel signatures identified by p0f, and protocol options, reflect software-dependent characteristics that may evolve with firmware, kernel, or configuration updates.

Rather than treating these variations as noise, IoT-ID incorporates them in a controlled manner by explicitly distinguishing between stable and dynamic attributes. A fingerprint is therefore considered valid at a given time instant t , representing the observed device state at that moment. When a subsequent fingerprint FP_{t+1} differs from FP_t , IoT-ID records a *state transition* rather than treating the change as an error.

Crucially, the system does not attempt to classify a transition as legitimate or malicious on its own; that judgment belongs to a higher-level policy layer. IoT-ID’s role is to make transitions visible, auditable, and attributable by explicitly identifying which attributes changed, at which layer, and when. A change confined to dynamic attributes (e.g., TCP window size or UPnP server string) is consistent with firmware or kernel updates and can be correlated with a known maintenance event. In contrast, a change in stable attributes (e.g., manufacturer, MSS, or baseline TTL) is anomalous by definition, since these reflect structural properties that should not change during normal operation, and therefore warrant immediate investigation. This two-tier model enables IoT-ID to support both lifecycle monitoring of expected evolution and security alerting for unexpected identity shifts, without conflating the two.

Security model. IoT-ID is designed to detect four classes of security-relevant events through fingerprint transitions. First, *stable-attribute anomalies*, namely changes in manufacturer, model, MSS, or baseline TTL, indicate events that cannot result from

legitimate software updates, such as unauthorized device replacement, MAC or identity spoofing, or hardware-level tampering. These events warrant immediate investigation regardless of context. Second, *dynamic-attribute transitions*, including changes in TCP window size, port signatures, or UPnP service strings, are consistent with firmware or kernel updates and are therefore flagged for correlation with known maintenance events registered in IoTEdu. Third, *fingerprint disappearance*, in which a previously observed device ceases to produce a fingerprint, may indicate physical removal, network reconfiguration, or denial of service. Fourth, *fingerprint collision introduction*, where a new device produces a fingerprint identical to an existing class, is expected for legitimate additions of the same model, but becomes anomalous in the absence of a corresponding procurement or deployment event.

Importantly, class-level fingerprint collisions among identical devices are not a security weakness but a deliberate property. They enable group-based vulnerability management, while the MAC address, maintained separately by IoTEdu, preserves instance-level accountability. The combination of deterministic fingerprint (*class identity*) and MAC address (*instance identity*) provides operators with the granularity required to answer both “is this device type affected by CVE-X?” and “which specific unit behaved unexpectedly at time t ?”

4. Experimental Setup and Data Collection

4.1. Experimental Environment and Evaluated Devices

The experimental evaluation was conducted in a controlled and reproducible environment using a VirtualBox-based virtualization platform. The host system consists of an Intel CPU with 2 GB of dedicated RAM, while network traffic was captured through the Intel 82540EM interface (`enp0s3`) configured in promiscuous mode to ensure full visibility of local communications. Data collection was performed on Linux Mint 22.3 (Zena), running kernel version `6.14.0-37-generic`, minimizing external variability during fingerprint acquisition. Table 3 summarizes the evaluated devices, including manufacturer, model, and operating system or kernel version when available. The dataset comprises heterogeneous device classes commonly found in IoT environments, such as smart TVs, TV boxes, smartphones, printers, and general-purpose computing devices, enabling the evaluation of IoT-ID under realistic conditions, including homogeneous network stacks and varying levels of device observability.

Table 3. Evaluated devices

Device	Manufacturer	Model	Qty.
Game Console	Microsoft	Xbox One	1
IP Camera	TP-Link	C500 (Model A)	3
IP Camera	Vix LED EXcelente	Speed Dome Solar (Model B)	1
Router	FiberHome	HG6143D	1
Router	TP-Link	EC220-G5	1
Smart Bulb	Avant NEO	RGB E27	1
Smart TV	TCL	UnionTV	1
Smart TV	TCL	Smart TV Pro	1
Smart TV	Samsung	UN32J4303	2
Smart TV	Samsung	QN55Q60TAGXZD	1
TV Box	Xiaomi	MiTV-AESP0	1
Wi-Fi Printer	HP	Deskjet 4640	1

4.2. Fingerprint Generation and Outputs

Fingerprint generation is performed by `bundle_snapshot.py`, which integrates active probing, traffic capture, feature extraction, and canonicalization into a unified pipeline. The tool receives the target IP, capture duration, output directory, and network interface as input, as illustrated below:

```
python3 iot_id.fingerprint.py runs [IP] --seconds 60 --iface "WIFI"
```

Optional parameters include `--mode` (target, default, or network) and `--canon_policy` (stable or rich), which define the discovery strategy and the attribute set used before hashing. Each execution produces the raw bundle (`fingerprint.json`), the canonical representation (`features_canon.json/.txt`), and the final digest (`fingerprint_sha256.txt`), explicitly separating observational data from the derived identity. By construction, identical inputs always generate identical fingerprints, ensuring reproducibility and reinforcing the deterministic nature of IoT-ID.

5. Experimental Results

The effectiveness of the proposed *IoT-ID* pipeline is evaluated using a dataset of 15 heterogeneous devices, including smart TVs, routers, cameras, a gaming console, and embedded IoT devices. The results reveal three distinct classes of behavior: (i) class-consistent fingerprints, (ii) cross-device signature collisions at L3/L4, and (iii) generic or low-entropy fingerprints.

Table 4 summarizes the extracted attributes and observed behavior for all devices. Across five consecutive executions per device, identical canonical representations and SHA-256 fingerprints were obtained, confirming the stability and reproducibility of the proposed method under consistent network conditions.

Table 4. Consolidated fingerprint attributes and observed behavior

Device	L7 (nmap)		L3/L4 (pcap_syn)			L4 (p0f)		Behavior
	manufacturer	model	mss	window	ttl	server sig	client sig	
Game Console	Microsoft	Xbox One	1460	65535	128	-	4:128+0:0:1460:65535,...	Unique
IP Camera Model A (1)	TP-Link	C500	1440	14400	64	-	-	Generic
IP Camera Model A (2)	TP-Link	C500	1440	14400	64	-	-	Class
IP Camera Model A (3)	TP-Link	C500	1440	14400	64	-	-	Class
IP Camera Model B	Vix LED EXcelente	Speed Dome Solar	-	-	64	-	-	Limited
Router FiberHome	FiberHome	HG6143D	1460	29200	64	-	-	Generic
Router TP-Link	TP-Link	EC220-G5	1460	14600	64	mss*10,...	-	Collision (Cross-device)
Smart Bulb	Avant NEO	RGB E27	-	-	255	-	-	Limited
Smart TV Samsung (1)	Samsung	UN32J4303	1460	14600	64	mss*10,...	-	Class
Smart TV Samsung (2)	Samsung	UN32J4303	1460	14600	64	mss*10,...	-	Class
Smart TV Samsung 55"	Samsung	QN55Q60TAGXZD	1460	29200	64	mss*20,...	-	Unique
Smart TV TCL (Smart TV Pro)	TCL	Smart TV Pro	1460	65535	64	4:64+0:0:1460:65535,...	-	Unique
Smart TV TCL (UnionTV)	TCL	UnionTV	1460	65535	64	4:64+0:0:1460:65535,...	-	Unique
TV Box Xiaomi	Xiaomi	MiTV-AESP0	1460	65535	64	4:64+0:0:1460:65535,...	-	Collision (L3/L4)
Wi-Fi Printer	HP	Deskjet 4640	1460	8760	64	mss*6,...	-	Unique

Class-consistent fingerprints. Devices sharing identical hardware and software configurations produce identical fingerprints, forming well-defined classes. This behavior is observed in the two Samsung UN32J4303 TVs, which exhibit identical L3/L4 attributes and identical p0f signatures, resulting in the same canonical representation and SHA-256 hash. A similar pattern is observed among IP cameras (1, 2, and 4), which share identical network parameters (MSS, TTL, and window size), indicating homogeneous firmware and network stacks. These results confirm that IoT-ID reliably captures device classes.

Cross-device collisions at L3/L4. The evaluation also reveals that distinct devices may share identical transport-layer characteristics. Notably, the Xiaomi MiTV and both

TCL TVs exhibit identical MSS (1460), TTL (64), window size (65535), and identical p0f signatures. Under traditional passive fingerprinting approaches, these devices would be indistinguishable. Additionally, the TP-Link router shares similar TCP characteristics with one of the Samsung TVs (window size 14600 and MSS scaling), demonstrating that such overlaps can occur even across device categories. IoT-ID resolves these ambiguities by incorporating application-layer attributes, producing distinct fingerprints despite identical L3/L4 behavior.

Generic and low-entropy devices. Some devices exhibit limited or non-distinctive attributes, resulting in generic fingerprints. The FiberHome router and multiple IP cameras expose only basic TCP/IP characteristics without application-layer metadata, reducing their identifiability. Similarly, each smart bulb and IP camera has an incomplete attribute set (e.g., missing MSS or window size), resulting in low-entropy fingerprints. These cases highlight the inherent limitations of passive fingerprinting in constrained IoT environments.

Device-specific signatures. Other devices exhibit distinctive patterns that enable clear identification. The Xbox One is characterized by a higher TTL (128) and a client-side SYN signature that includes advanced TCP options (e.g., window scaling). The Wi-Fi printer presents a non-standard TCP configuration, including a window size derived from $MSS \times 6$ and the absence of the DF flag, both of which are characteristic of embedded or RTOS-based stacks.

Overall, the results demonstrate that multi-layer canonicalization effectively balances generalization and discrimination: identical devices are consistently grouped into classes, while heterogeneous devices are correctly distinguished even under identical transport-layer conditions.

5.1. Discussion

The results in Table 5 confirm a key property of deterministic fingerprinting: devices with identical manufacturer, model, firmware, and network stack parameters produce the same SHA-256 fingerprint. For example, *TV Samsung (1)* and *TV Samsung (2)* share the fingerprint `1f4e8c4a...`, while the three units of IP Camera Model A, instances (1), (2), and (3), share `c61f2883...`. These repetitions are therefore expected outcomes of equivalent attribute sets rather than accidental collisions.

Table 5. Devices and their corresponding SHA-256 fingerprints

Device	SHA-256 Fingerprint
TV TCL (UnionTV)	994f131342176c20415565dab0adf2666b160422d3df1511c0a37ae135985add
Router FiberHome	14407342dc69a801f52f6cead97d00e5260b7206072f145e6fde19e07cb1f157
Smart Bulb	993e9afc860d624a332822679ea4efc3490c2734ba84ad160c8d36abf0d546f7
TV TCL (Smart TV Pro)	e20c48257b98e86fa11d7c4444e7e5da7176a1b328719ea5f46f831951392d51
TV Samsung (1)	1f4e8c4af2be567b929cf5b7409c57d648ea062262eeab566e11e32c1b437e94
TV Xiaomi	6397f4729927379fde73d5c1ea234ef1070d3785b4f271c562fa4cb688be2d48
TV Samsung 55"	410528d091cb14cea300d79e74348087fc3a1b351584c919650c3a6f24ec18d1
Printer	93ef878c8f2de4eab5a5c780b1dc146d28df337116d8e93019bd9f4cc78c41df
Xbox One	50f1736613c079a70b2d094c680cd8f9027adeb34ca7e90e7c4322a73492eb01
TV Samsung (2)	1f4e8c4af2be567b929cf5b7409c57d648ea062262eeab566e11e32c1b437e94
Router TP-Link	dce0ee76d22f60bec93ce4f6478a9ffe439b2b6e914bafbafe0048685402b2cc
IP Camera Model A (1)	c61f28839b696b65307cef2db341e976fadf10012d9c0f01f6a490b1e3e5742f
IP Camera Model A (2)	c61f28839b696b65307cef2db341e976fadf10012d9c0f01f6a490b1e3e5742f
IP Camera Model A (3)	c61f28839b696b65307cef2db341e976fadf10012d9c0f01f6a490b1e3e5742f
IP Camera Model B	5b60133e2971f571f7a4ceadd55041a78771b65189e64c0f891eb687ab37bc74

Within the IoTedu architecture, this property is not a limitation but a deliberate

design choice. The fingerprint acts as a *class identifier*, capturing the structural identity of a device type rather than its physical instance. Combined with the MAC address, the system provides dual granularity: *instance-level uniqueness* through hardware identifiers and *class-level grouping* through deterministic fingerprints, supporting both precise asset tracking and scalable device management.

Operationally, devices sharing the same fingerprint can be managed as a homogeneous group. For example, all devices associated with `c61f2883...` (IP cameras) can be jointly assessed for vulnerabilities or firmware updates, reducing overhead in large-scale deployments.

The canonical model explicitly separates stable and dynamic attributes, making state transitions interpretable rather than merely detectable. Stable attributes, such as manufacturer, model, MSS, and baseline TTL, define the invariant identity core; changes in these attributes are structurally anomalous and may indicate hardware replacement, spoofing, or misconfiguration. In contrast, dynamic attributes, such as TCP window size, `poF` signatures, and service strings, are expected to evolve with software updates and can be validated against maintenance records. This separation enables continuous monitoring without false positives during routine updates, while preserving full transition visibility for operator validation.

The evaluation also reveals inherent limitations outside typical IoT environments. General-purpose systems, such as Windows-based notebooks, often expose highly standardized network stacks, leading to generic fingerprints and unavoidable collisions that restrict identification to the device class or operating system. The lack of rich application-layer metadata aggravates this issue. Similarly, modern smartphones employ privacy-preserving mechanisms that reduce the observable feature space, resulting in incomplete scans and inconsistent fingerprints. These findings reflect a fundamental trade-off between identifiability and privacy, indicating that such scenarios may require lower granularity or complementary temporal and behavioral analysis.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented IoT-ID³, a deterministic fingerprinting approach for IoT device identification based on a hybrid pipeline that combines application-layer metadata with transport-layer signatures. Its main contribution is a canonical representation that enables reproducible, auditable device identities via cryptographic hashing. The results show that transport-layer attributes support coarse-grained classification but are insufficient for uniquely identifying device instances in environments with homogeneous network stacks. By integrating multi-layer canonicalization, IoT-ID resolves these ambiguities, as demonstrated by the differentiation of devices with identical transport signatures.

Our findings also show that device identity emerges from cross-layer correlation. Variations in protocol behavior, such as TCP window scaling across Samsung models and simplified RTOS-based stacks, confirm the value of combining heterogeneous attributes into a unified representation. At the same time, the evaluation highlights intrinsic limitations in non-IoT environments, where privacy mechanisms and software homogeneity reduce the discriminative power of features and hinder stable fingerprint generation. Future

³https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbr26_fingerprint

work includes temporal and learning-based techniques, expanded discovery protocols, TLS/SSL metadata, and broader validation in real-world enterprise environments.

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